

PEDAGOGY OF COOPERATION – AS AN EDUCATIONAL CONCEPT OF THE XXI CENTURY. CONCEPT FOR FORMING INCLUSIVE READINESS OF TEACHERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12599660>

Abstract. *The paper presents the basic ideas of the concept of forming an inclusive readiness of the future pedagogues-defectologists. The effectiveness of inclusive education is seen as providing equal access to education for all students, given the diversity of special educational needs and individual capabilities, which provides psychological and pedagogical formed (inclusive) readiness of teachers to intersectoral cooperation with all stakeholders inclusive educational environment.*

Keywords: *pedagogues-defectologists, bilateral allocations, multidisciplinary, multidisciplinary.*

Inclusive willingness of a pedagogue is defined as a complex integral subjective quality of a person, which is revealed through meaningful complex competencies and determines the possibility of a creative professional and pedagogical activities in the real world.

Uzbekistan began the process of including children with special needs in general education institutions soon after gaining independence [1.2.3.]. The country participates in a number of important international agreements, such as the Convention on the Rights of the Child (ratified in 1992), the Dakar “Framework for Global Action on Education”, and the “Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities”. The European Union project “Inclusive education for children with special needs in Uzbekistan” was implemented in the republic; the overall objective of this project was “to improve the quality of education for children with special needs aged 2–10 years and to promote their integration into general education kindergartens and primary schools Uzbekistan”. The purpose of the support provided by the European Union, as noted in the strategy document for Central Asia, was to promote stability and security in the countries of Central Asia, support their aspirations for sustainable economic development, reduce poverty and promote closer regional cooperation in Central Asia itself, as well as between Central Asia and the EU. Uzbekistan received bilateral allocations under the next Development Cooperation Instrument, as well as the right to receive assistance under regional and thematic programs. The project carried out its activities in 4 components, where the 2nd component of the project is “capacity building”, i.e. training and retraining of teachers and other specialists for inclusive education. According to the database of the Ministry of Public Education and the Center for Secondary Specialized Vocational Education, international donor organizations implemented more than 30 projects that were aimed at increasing access to quality education for children and adolescents. The development of inclusive education in Uzbekistan began in 1996. At first, inclusive education was considered only as the integration

of children with special needs into mainstream schools. However, over time, inclusive education technologies began to be used more and more often, which were based on the principles of equal access to education, regardless of multidisciplinary

The effectiveness of inclusive education (“ensuring equal access to education for all students, taking into account the diversity of special educational needs and individual capabilities” [6]) is ensured by the formed psychological and pedagogical (inclusive) readiness of the teacher for effective interaction with all subjects of the inclusive educational space. The inclusive readiness of a teacher is defined as a complex integral subjective quality of a person, which is meaningfully revealed through a set of competencies and determines the possibility of effective professional and pedagogical activity in current conditions [6,7], and is the most important determinant that ensures the possibility of creating conditions for teaching “special” children in a mass environment. schools. The subject of the proposed concept is the new content of educational effects (inclusive readiness) and educational results (a set of competencies that determines the content of inclusive readiness) of higher pedagogical education. The content of educational effects and educational results reflects the state and requirements made by consumers (individuals, society, state) of an educational service for its quality. The content of educational results captures a set of competencies that determine the success of professional activity [4.5.6,7], and the content of educational effects presupposes formed intentions (readiness) to use them in solving practical problems in current professional conditions. When preparing the concept for the formation of inclusive readiness of teachers, theoretical methods were used: analysis of scientific-methodological, psychological-pedagogical literature, educational standards of higher education (first stage), standard curricula and discipline curricula. An analysis of the literature showed that the formation of teacher readiness is considered, on the one hand, from the standpoint of the content of the object of readiness, on the other, from the point of view of the methodology and tools of the process of its formation. One cannot but agree with the opinions of the authors who consider the formation of certain aspects of professional pedagogical readiness from the standpoint of systemic, axiological, acmeological, personal-activity approaches (L. V. Antropova, T. K. Bolev, O. A. Larionova, M. I. Lukyanova, P.V. Seredenko, A.B. Serykh, N.A. Tarasyuk, V.V. Khitryuk, etc.). The competency-based approach is traditionally considered in connection with the problem of developing professional competence [4], [5], [6], [7]. In accordance with the State educational standard for the training of specialists at the first stage of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, three groups of competencies are defined: academic (mastery of the methodology and terminology of a particular field of knowledge, understanding of the systemic relationships operating in it, as well as the ability to use them in solving practical problems), professional (readiness and ability to act expediently in accordance with the requirements of a real pedagogical situation), social and personal (a set of competencies related to the person himself as an individual, the interaction of the individual with other people, the group and society). This allows us to consider the problem of developing inclusive readiness from the perspective of a competency-based approach. The fundamental ideas of the concept of developing inclusive readiness of teachers are based on an understanding of the essence of the phenomenon of “inclusive readiness of a teacher” and the requirements that it must satisfy. The readiness of future teachers to work in conditions of educational inclusion must meet the following requirements: be a mandatory educational “effect” of the professional training of future teachers; reflect psychological and pedagogical aspects; be consistent with educational results (a set of specialist

competencies) and ensure the possibility of their implementation in professional and pedagogical activities; correspond to the sociocultural and humanistic context; focus on the socialization of all children, including children with special educational needs (SEN), as a means and result of their inclusion in the educational space and society; ensure professional and pedagogical confidence, determine effective models of cooperation, interaction and communication between the teacher and all participants in the process of inclusive education; rely on the professional and pedagogical training of future teachers, recognition and acceptance of the values of inclusive education, a tolerant attitude towards all participants in the educational space; determine the role and functions of the teacher in the social partnership of parties interested in inclusive education, as well as their professional communication to ensure effective support of a child with special education needs in the inclusive educational space; ensure the professional competence of future teachers. The concept of forming inclusive readiness of future teachers is a system of scientifically based views that reflect an understanding of the competency-based essence of inclusive readiness as an educational effect and an action strategy for its formation in the educational space of a higher education institution based on a competency-based approach [4], [5], [6], [7].

The educational situation in the republic and the educational space of higher education institutions satisfy the above requirements and are able to create conditions for the formation of the readiness of future teachers to work in conditions of inclusive education.

The concept of forming inclusive readiness of teachers in the educational space of a higher education institution is based on groups of general pedagogical and specific principles. Among the general pedagogical principles, the following principles should be mentioned:

- the principle of humanization, which defines the value of a child's life as the main priority;
- the principle of a value-based attitude towards the personality of each child in the educational and social space (creation of an environment of tolerant communication and interaction, recognition of the right to "otherness" ("he is the Other") and respect for the individual characteristics of each);
- the principle of recognition of democratic ideas in the educational space (freedom and the right to choose an educational institution for all students and the opportunity for all children to receive an education);
- the principle of scientific support for the process of forming inclusive readiness of future teachers (description of the conceptual basis of the process of forming inclusive readiness, its components, competency-based content, etc.);
- the principle of consistency, which defines the process of forming inclusive readiness of teachers as a system of work aimed at developing each of its aspects (psychological and pedagogical) and structural components (cognitive, emotional, motivational-conative, communicative, reflective) through mastering the necessary knowledge, skills, and methods of activity, competencies and the ability to use them in professional and pedagogical activities;
- the principle of integrity, which reveals substantive continuity in mastering the theoretical and practical content of academic disciplines, the sequence of formation of knowledge, skills, and competencies;
- the principle of multidisciplinary, which presupposes interdisciplinary integration of the content of academic disciplines, allowing us to consider the ideas of inclusive education in a multifaceted and diverse manner.

Specific principles for the formation of inclusive readiness are:

- the principle of accepting the social model of disability as a priority, in which developmental disorders and the “otherness” of the child are considered as an option for the manifestation of individuality;

- the principle of preventive adaptation of future teachers to new conditions of professional pedagogical activity (modeling in the educational space of the university the conditions of real teaching activity and work in the conditions of inclusive education);

- the principle of social support and interaction (participation of all stakeholders (participants of the inclusive educational space and the entire social environment) in planning, promoting ideas and implementing inclusive education);

- the principle of diagnosing professional and pedagogical difficulties and their prevention (identifying “bottlenecks” of individual inclusive readiness of future teachers and their compensation);

- the principle of forming a team style of professional pedagogical thinking and problem solving (joint discussion and solution of learning problems, correction of violations and minimizing the difficulties of a child with special education needs with a teacher-defectologist, educational psychologist, social educator, etc.).

The concept being developed provides a strategic solution to the problem of developing inclusive readiness of teachers in the educational space of a higher education institution.

However, efforts and achievements to support inclusive legal frameworks, as well as policy documentation reflecting the desire for educational inclusion of children with special needs, remain quite fragmented.

The implementation of previous projects had a somewhat highly specialized approach, and often took place without the participation of society and non-governmental organizations. The implementation of previous projects had a somewhat highly specialized approach, and often took place without the participation of society and government organizations. As a result, not all development strategies were continued after the end of financial support from donor organizations. It is significant in this regard that the term “special needs” is not used consistently across government documents, and where it is used, its application is not always consistent.

In this regard, consistent improvement of interdepartmental coordination and mutual cooperation is necessary. Likewise, the concept of “inclusive education” has different meanings and is not always part of a common approach. This fact concerns experts participating in the educational process, parents, as well as the rest of the public. The differences between concepts such as “integration”, “adaptation” and “inclusiveness” are not entirely clear to the general public. As a result, the development of inclusiveness in Uzbekistan often lacks consistent methodological guidance, which largely places the implementation process on the personal interests of teachers and/or parents.

In addition, the issue of checking the quality of services provided in the field of inclusive education in Uzbekistan remains not fully resolved. This is explained by the fact that quality assessment and control in the system of inclusive educational services, as well as for existing general and specialized education, cannot exist separately from formal training requirements. The educational services provided must be monitored and evaluated and include a quality assurance mechanism where the “best interests of the child” must be taken into account. However, efforts and achievements to support inclusive legal frameworks, as well as policy documentation reflecting the desire for educational inclusion of children with special needs, remain quite

fragmented. Implementation of previous projects took a somewhat ad hoc approach, and often took place without public participation and non-governmental organizations. The implementation of previous projects had a somewhat highly specialized approach, and often took place without the participation of society and non-governmental organizations. As a result, not all development strategies were continued after the end of financial support from donor organizations. It is significant in this regard that the term “special needs” is not used consistently across government documents, and where it is used, its application is not always consistent. In this regard, consistent improvement of interdepartmental coordination and mutual cooperation is necessary. Likewise, the concept of “inclusive education” has different meanings and is not always part of a common approach. This fact concerns experts participating in the educational process, parents, as well as the rest of the public. The differences between concepts such as “integration”, “adaptation” and “inclusiveness” are not entirely clear to the general public. As a result, the development of inclusiveness in Uzbekistan often lacks consistent methodological guidance, which largely places the implementation process on the personal interests of teachers and/or parents.

Summing up, in conclusion I would like to especially raise the issue of checking the quality of services provided in the field of inclusive education in Uzbekistan, where it remains incompletely resolved. This is explained by the fact that quality assessment and control in the system of inclusive educational services, as well as for existing general and specialized education, cannot exist separately from formal training requirements. The educational services provided must be monitored and evaluated and include a quality assurance mechanism where the “best interests of the child” must be taken into account.

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